

Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient from Success: A New Approach for Robot-Assisted Suturing

1st Marco Caianiello, 2nd Cristina Iacono, 3rd Antonella Imperato, 4th Fanny Ficuciello

Universita degli Studi di Napoli, Federico II

Naples, Italy

{name.surname}@unina.it

Abstract—Robot-assisted minimally invasive surgery (RAMIS) has improved the quality of operations, execution time, and patient recovery time. However, suturing remains a tedious, complex, and time-consuming task. To automate this procedure, we have investigated the use of Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) to generate a trajectory for Wound-Approaching (WA). The trajectory must satisfy surgical constraints, be neither too long nor too wide, and minimize recovery time and side effects. We compare standard DDPG, DDPG from Demonstration (DDPGfD), and we have developed a new algorithm that learns from success epochs, DDPG from Success (DDPGfS). An ad hoc reward function was developed to minimize the number of actions and avoid undesirable behaviour in the neighbourhood of the wound. Among the algorithms, DDPGfS proves to be the best choice in terms of reliability and robustness with a percentage of success equal to 74% respect to 64% of DDPGfD. The new dense reward function enhance the performance, either in low support situation, preventing the agent to oscillate around the entry point.

Index Terms—Robotic Surgery, Deep Reinforcement Learning, Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of robotic instrumentation in Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS) has greatly improved surgical outcomes, operation times, and patient recovery. Ongoing research in this field aims to automate tedious and complex tasks, relieving surgeons of their burden. However, the suturing task is still one of the most challenging and time-consuming tasks in Robot Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery (RAMIS). The suturing task can be divided into five basic points: (1) Needle recognition and grasping; (2) Needle positioning; (3) Needle insertion; (4) Needle re-grasping; (5) Knot-tying. According to medical guidelines, the sub-task (2) is essential in suturing to minimize tissue stress, side effects, and promote rapid patient recovery. A correct needle positioning is defined by orthogonality between the needle tip and the wound entry point Fig. 1.

In this study, we investigate the feasibility of employing Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to tackle the Wound-Approaching (WA) problem by assessing its ability to generate trajectories that are both suitable and practical for real suturing tasks. DRL can solve complex tasks under various constraints, but the exploration by the agent is a critical aspect because it directly affects the solution and the training time, especially for the RAMIS application. Discretization is not an appropriate method for surgical applications in either case, so a continuous approach must be used. The Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient

Fig. 1. Representation of the experimental setup in a simulation environment. The Patience Side Manipulator (PSM) hold the needle while the need holder SNAP fix the needle position respect to the gripper. The middle tip tangent vector that define the surgical the surgical constraints respect the Suture Plane is shown in yellow.

(DDPG) algorithm is a suitable DRL technique for such applications. It works with the State Space and the Action Space in the continuous domain. To address the exploration problem, offline demonstration can be used as a guide for the agent during the exploration and learning process, reducing exploration time and achieving early policy improvements [1]. However, the Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient from Demonstrations (DDPGfD) does not consider the critical aspects of surgical applications and environments. In order to improve these aspects, we have incorporated the robot's joint limits and the length of the trajectory in a novel dense reward function. In addition, we developed a new training technique called DDPG from Success (DDPGfS) to improve the agent's exploration behavior. This approach allows the algorithm to learn from successful episodes and use this knowledge to strengthen its training.

II. METHOD

A. Learning from Success

In the DDPGfD the Demonstration Buffer is stored alongside the Replay Buffer and accelerates the learning and the exploration in the workspace. Both simulations [2] and real scenarios can be utilized to obtain data offline. On the other hand, we introduce the concept of a Success Buffer (\mathcal{S}) alongside the Replay Buffer (\mathcal{R}). By probabilistically sampling from \mathcal{S} or \mathcal{R} during training, using probabilities ϵ_s and ϵ_x , respectively

TABLE I
DDPG, DDPGfD AND DDPGfS RESULTS

Algorithm	Δt_{\min}	Δt_{\max}	%L	%T	\hat{a}_{\min}	\hat{a}_{\max}	r_{\min}	r_{\max}
DDPG	4.8s	5.7s	20%	70%	97	104	1210	2401
DDPGfD $\epsilon_d = 0.4$	4.8s	7.2s	63%	100%	97	97	1049	1049
DDPGfD $\epsilon_d = 0.7$	4.8s	7.2s	65%	100%	97	97	1740	1740
DDPGfS $\epsilon_s = 0.4$	4.8s	5.36s	59%	100%	97	109	1740	2337
DDPGfS $\epsilon_s = 0.7$	4.8s	7.2s	74%	100%	97	97	1049	1101

Fig. 2. (A) DDPG epoch reward; (B) DDPGfD epoch reward with $\epsilon_d = 0.4$; (C) DDPGfD epoch reward with $\epsilon_d = 0.7$; (D) DDPGfS epoch reward with $\epsilon_s = 0.4$; (E) DDPGfS epoch reward with $\epsilon_s = 0.7$;

(where $\epsilon_s + \epsilon_x = 1$), successful epochs can be prioritized. To handle the challenge of storing tuples during an epoch when the goal achievement is unknown, we propose a Temporary Buffer (\mathcal{T}) that holds all the tuples generated. At the end of an epoch, if the goal is reached, \mathcal{T} is loaded into \mathcal{S} ; otherwise, it is loaded into \mathcal{R} . This approach allows the agent to learn without prior knowledge of the task or constraints.

B. Reward Function

The reward function $r_t \in \mathbb{R}$ is modeled on the Coulomb law. It is highly dependent on the agent's learning, and it accounts for four possible scenarios where Fail occur when the robot is in an invalid pose and Max Action happen when the number of action executed, $n_{act,t}$, is equal to maximum allowed, $n_{act,max}$. The dependency with $n_{act,t}$ prevents the agent from oscillating around the goal without reaching it and promotes the path with the minimum number of actions. The shape of the reward function is

$$r_t = r_{t-1} + \begin{cases} 1000 & \text{Success} \\ -245 & \text{Fail} \\ -5n_{act,max} & \text{Max Action} \\ \frac{n_{act,max} - n_{act,t}}{100 \|S_t - S_g\|^2} & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

III. RESULTS

The experimental environment consists of a da Vinci Research Kit (dVRK) equipped with a Patient Side Manipulator (PSM), a needle with a circular cross-section of 1 cm radius, a fake wound and need holder, Fig. 1. To avoid damages or danger situation, the learning process has been carried out in a simulation environment [2], [3]. The policy learned must

generate a trajectory with a maximum position error $e_{p,max} = 1$ mm and maximum orientation error $e_{o,max} = 0.0872$ rad ($\sim 5^\circ$). The starting pose is generated randomly with maximum displacement from the goal pose of 2.5 ± 0.5 cm for position and 0.4 ± 0.1 rad ($\sim 28^\circ$) for orientation to ensure generalization. In Fig. 2 we compare the training results of DDPG, DDPGfD, and DDPGfS. After completing the training phase, 300 epochs, we conducted an additional validation step by testing each algorithm for an additional 100 epochs. The parameters evaluated are the execution time (Δt), success rate during learning (%L) and after learning (%T), number of actions (\hat{a}), and reward value (r), Tab. I. The results suggest crucial role of the goal-oriented approach. For this reason, the DDPG performs the worst without it. Interestingly, when $\epsilon_s = \epsilon_d = 0.7$, the performance of DDPGfD and DDPGfS was comparable. This show that our proposed algorithm can achieve a good solution without requiring any demonstrations. Additionally, DDPGfS exhibited the ability to improve its solution epoch by epoch. This outcome was made possible by r_t that reduces n_{act} and prevents uncontrolled behavior.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we explore the use of DDPG, DDPGfD, and DDPGfS supported by a novel reward function r_t in order to determine the optimal approach for WA. We find that DDPGfD performs better than the others for needle positioning, achieving good results with $\epsilon_d = 0.4$. On the other side, DDPGfS perform the best for $\epsilon_s = 0.7$ reaching optimally the goal with zero prior knowledge and making it a valuable compromise between reliability, robustness, and computational efficiency. Our future work includes to introduce a human-based quality index and incorporate suturing sub-goals r_t .

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Nair, B. McGrew, M. Andrychowicz, W. Zaremba, and P. Abbeel, "Overcoming exploration in reinforcement learning with demonstrations," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2018, pp. 6292–6299.
- [2] G. A. Fontanelli, M. Selvaggio, M. Ferro, F. Ficuciello, M. Vendittelli, and B. Siciliano, "A v-rep simulator for the da vinci research kit robotic platform," in *2018 7th IEEE International Conference on Biomedical Robotics and Biomechatronics (Biorob)*, 2018, pp. 1056–1061.
- [3] G. A. Fontanelli, F. Ficuciello, L. Villani, and B. Siciliano, "Modelling and identification of the da vinci research kit robotic arms," in *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 1464–1469.